
ANALYSIS OF SELECTED FINANCIAL MARKET PLAYER'S CREDIT FACILITIES ON HUMAN DEVELOPMENT INDEX IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: This study evaluated the relationship between credit extension of selected financial market players like commercial banks, finance houses, development banks and market capitalization and human development index in Nigeria, using Human development Index (HDI) as the dependent variable and commercial bank lending, finance house lending, Development bank lending and market capitalization as independent variables. The researcher made use of secondary data sourced from the annual reports of Nigerian Export and Import Bank (NEXIM) and the CBN statistical bulletin for various years. The data were analyzed descriptively, while the hypotheses were tested using multiple regression. The result of the analysis showed that only commercial bank lending has positive and significant relationship with HDI. Finance house lending and Market Capitalization have negative and insignificant relationship with HDI, while DBL has positive but insignificant relationship with HDI, thus, the low HDI in Nigeria. To curb this ugly situation, the monetary authority has to develop and implement investor friendly policy for development bank, finance houses, and capital market, because only the commercial banks cannot meet up with the fund requirement of Nigerians.

Key words: human development index, market capitalization, deficit unit, finance houses, Development bank.

Introduction

Units are describing as different types of parties in financial transaction such as the lenders and the borrowers (Brian 2022). The borrowers are regarded as deficit units while the lenders are seen as the surplus unit. The deficit unit is an economic unit which has viable investment project and business ideas, but lacks funding for executing such projects. This deficit unit could be individuals, households, companies or institutions, government and countries. On the other hand, the surplus unit is an economic unit with income that is greater than or equal to expenditures on consumption throughout a period (Will, 2021). A surplus unit earns more than it spends on its basic needs and therefore has money left over to invest or save (James & Henry, 2015). This surplus unit like the deficit unit could be individuals, households, companies, institutions, government and countries who decides to benefit from lending to surplus units. To bridge the financial gap, deficit units do borrow from the surplus unit at a stipulated cost known as interest that is always expressed as a percentage of the borrowed fund.

The flow of funds from the deficit sector to the surplus sector will lead to an increase in economic development (UNDP, 2024). Economic development can be seen as efforts that seek to improve the economic well-being and

quality of life for an economy by creating and retaining jobs, and supporting or growing incomes (Bartholomew 2016).

In between the surplus and deficit unit lies the financial intermediaries that facilitates the transfer of money from deficit units to the surplus units. These financial intermediaries are the financial market players which could be inform of banks and other financial institutions such as finance houses and capital markets. This market players are meant to provide access to wealth that will improve the standard of living for everyone by transferring funds from surplus units to deficit units (David 2012), and globally commercial banks play a vital role in achieving such goal. (Cavugil, Knight, Riesenberger, Rammal & Rose, 2014).

In Nigeria's financial system, there are many financial institutions in existence that are designated to extend credit facilities to the deficit unit, such as development banks, Commercial banks, finance houses, capital market etc. Considering the difficulty in accessing funds and the rate of poverty that is prevalent in the country, the researcher becomes worrisome if all these financial system players actually play the financial intermediation roles appropriately for the benefits of the proposed deficit units, especially at individual level. Hence, this study seeks to evaluate the effect of select financial system players credit facilities like development bank, commercial banks, finance houses and capital market on Human development index (HDI) in Nigeria by examining the relationship between commercial bank lending and Human development index, Analyzing the relationship between finance house lending and Human development index, evaluating the relationship between development bank lending and Human development index and ascertaining the relationship between market capitalization and Human development index in Nigeria. To that effect, the study hypothesizes that commercial bank lending, finance house lending, Development bank lending and market capitalization have no significant relationship with human development index in Nigeria.

Literature Review

Development Banks

A development bank is a bank specifically established with the purpose of providing long-term financing for various development projects, which help to accelerate economic development in a country or region. Development banks are often established and owned by government or non-profit organizations to finance projects that would otherwise not be able to get financing from commercial lenders. These institutions are known to play a crucial role in the rapid industrialization of an economy (Beatriz 1999).

These banks provide medium and long-term loans to prospective investors in the areas of agriculture, industry, and commerce. According to Aliyu and Yusuf (2014), most developmental projects require long-term loans, since commercial banks only provide short term loans, development banks fill the gap by providing medium- and long-term capital to entrepreneurs to finance their enterprises.

Development banks in Nigeria include Bank of Agriculture, Bank of industry, Federal Mortgage bank of Nigeria, The Infrastructure bank of Nigeria.

Commercial Bank Lending

Commercial bank lending is one of the ways through which the deficit unit acquires funds from the deficit units. They lend on short-, medium- or long-term basis to individuals, business organization and governments in order to enable them embark on investment and development activities as means of aiding their growth in particular

or contributing towards the economic development of a country in general (Goldsmith, 2009). These loans often require collateral, usually in the form of property, plant or equipment which the bank can confiscate from the borrower in the event of default or bankruptcy (Will, 2020). These commercial banks loan can be in form of lines of credit, term loans, lease financing, commercial mortgages, acquisition loans (Katie, 2021)

Finance Houses

A finance house is a company concerned with providing small loans to people. They engage in the provision of hire purchase and other forms of installment credit like mortgage loans.

Finance companies play a key role in fulfilling the gap of financial services that are not generally provided by the banking sector (Enofe, Osa-Erabor & Ehiorobo, 2013). The importance of finance houses can be emphasized from the structure of the financial system. In the financial system of most countries commercial banks do play a dominant role in mobilizing funds and using these resources for investment, but due to the structural limitations and rigidity that are prevalent in operations banks, bank could not expand their operations in all expected areas and were confined to a relatively limited sphere of financial services. Moreover, their efforts to meet long term financing with short term resources may result in asset-liability mismatch which can create pressure on their financial assets. These drawbacks led to the emergence of non-bank financial institutions for supporting industrialization and economic development of the country such as finance houses (Atutu & Bello, 1999).

Capital Market Operations

Capital market is a place where buyers and sellers indulge in the buying and selling of securities like bonds, stocks etc. The trading is undertaken by individuals and institutions. Capital market trades mostly in long-term securities. The magnitude of nation's capital market is directly interconnected to the size of its economy which means that ripples in one corner can cause major waves somewhere else (Gregotian & Ghosh, 2007). One of the indexes of capital market is market capitalization.

Market capitalization, sometimes referred to as market cap, is the total value of a publicly traded company's outstanding common shares owned by stockholders. Market capitalization is equal to the market price per common share multiplied by the number of common shares outstanding. Generally, the capitalization rate can be viewed as a measure of risk. So determining whether a higher or lower cap rate is better will depend on the investor and their risk profile. A higher cap rate means that the investment holds more risk whereas a low cap risk means an investment holds less risk. As July 2024, the value of Nigerian market capitalization is 34.455 USD bn (investopedia.com, 2024)

Human Development Index (HDI)

It is the summary composite measure of a country's average achievements in three basic aspects of human development (health, knowledge and standard of living). The health is assessed by the life expectancy at birth, the education dimension is measured by mean of years of schooling for adults and expected years of schooling for children. The standard of living dimension is measured by gross national income per capita (UNDP, 2024). The HDI sets a minimum and maximum for each dimension, called goalposts, then shows where each country stands in relation to these goalposts. This is expressed as a value between 0 and 1. The higher the HDI, the better for the economy. A high HDI essentially means that the country in question offers a generally high

standard of living, with decent healthcare, education, and opportunities to earn money, so the higher a country's human development, the higher its HDI value. Currently the Nigerian HDI has a low value of 0.548 with 33% of Nigerians living within poverty line (UNDP Nigeria, (2024)

Deficit Sector

Deficit sectors are individuals, business or government who has spending plans in excess of their income; consequently, they are interested in borrowing funds. So, funds flow from the surplus sector of the economy, to the financial Institutions, and from the financial institutions to the deficit sector of the economy. These funds are therefore invested into the economy in the form of businesses, and infrastructure, which will lead to an increase in economic growth and development (Olaniyi, 2017).

Empirical Review

Some related literatures were reviewed in the course of this research work. Bassey (2022) examined that commercial bank loan is one of the factors that provide economic growth. This is because the availability and affordability of bank loans induces investment which in turn increases employment, income, output hence economic growth in Nigeria. Okechukwu and Elizabeth (2016) opined that commercial banks significantly and positively play better roles towards fund mobilization for economic development through capital accumulation, mobilization of savings, availability of fund, financing industry, optimum utilization of resources. Julia (2023) opined that commercial banks make money by providing and earning interest from loans such as mortgages, auto loans, business loans, personal loans. The study concludes that commercial banks are important to the economy because they create capital, credit, and liquidity in the market. Adoms (2022) concludes that commercial bank-credit has a strong impact on economic development and human development index in Nigeria. Enofe, Osa-Erhabor and Ehiorobo (2013) examined the effect of CBN and Finance houses activities on economic growth in Nigeria, and concludes that finance companies through their activities accumulate capital which are channeled to the productive sectors for increased productivity and output. Thus, there is a significant relationship between finance houses activities and economic development. Iwudu (2022), opined that there is a long run relationship between mortgage financing and economic growth. Mortgage loans provide finance to purchase real estates. Thus, human development index assumes that a good shelter is one of the measures of welfare. Stephens (2020) asserts that market capitalization and all shares index exerted a positive but insignificant influence on economic growth in Nigeria, while the total value of transactions exert a positive and significant influence on economic growth. Market capitalization is one of the indicators of the capital market in any given economy. Edame, Greg, Okoro and Uchenna (2013) opined that the capital market is a driver of economic growth and development because it is essential for the long-term growth formation. It is crucial in the mobilization of savings and channeling of such savings to profitable self-liquidating investments. Briggs (2015) examined that the capital market and economic growth are co-related. This indicates that a long run relationship exists between the capital market and economic growth. Cross (2020) concludes that capital market plays a major role in driving the Nigerian economy forward. An efficient capital market facilitates economic growth by ensuring the smooth movement of funds in the economy.

Methodology

This is a developmental research work that seeks to evaluate the impact of development bank lending, commercial bank lending finance house bank lending and capital market (proxies by market capitalization) on human development in Nigeria for a period of twelve years (2010 to 2021), using human development index as the dependent variable and development bank lending, commercial bank lending, finance house lending and market capitalization as independent variables.

This research work made use of secondary data only sourced from different relevant publications like Nigerian export and import bank (NEXIMB), Central Bank of Nigerian Statistical Bulletin, published journals and other relevant sources.

The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, while the stated hypotheses were tested using multiple regression technique with the help of E-views version 12.0

The model for this research work is formulated mathematically as follows;

$$\text{HDI} = f(\text{vDBL}) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

$$\text{HDI} = F(\text{vCBL}) \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

$$\text{HDI} = F(\text{vFCH}) \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

$$\text{HDI} = F(\text{vMCAP}) \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

Where;

HDI = Human development index

vDBL = Value of development bank lending

vCBL = Value of commercial bank lending

vFCH = Value of finance house lending

MCAP = Market capitalization

Having logged the data, the econometric model can be expressed as;

$$\text{LogHDI} = b_0 + b_1 \log \text{DBL} + U_t \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

$$\text{LogHDI} = b_0 + b_1 \log \text{CBL} + U_t \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

$$\text{LogHDI} = b_0 + b_1 \log, \text{FCH} + U_t \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

$$\text{LogHDI} = b_0 + b_1 \log \text{MCAP} + U_t \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

Data Presentation

Table 1: Variables of interest 2010 to 2021

YEAR	HDI	CBL	FCH	NEXIM	MKC
2010	0.5	7,018.27	30.65	7,637,308	9,918.21
2011	0.51	6,685.85	33.36	12,851,587	10,275.34
2012	0.51	7,723.72	23.77	19,505,114	14,800.94
2013	0.52	9,467.28	46.68	28,947,019	19,077.42
2014	0.53	12,101.20	48.81	37,566,171	16,875.10
2015	0.53	12,101.32	49.62	44,061,658	17,003.39
2016	0.53	14,752.84	40.58	41,577,420	16,185.73
2017	0.53	14,513.32	40.9	40,753,837	21,128.90
2018	0.54	13,779.50	54.15	44,249,701	21,904.04
2019	0.54	15,748.33	80.13	62,992,804	25,890.22
2020	0.539	18,122.51	113.55	85,706,366	38,589.58
2021	0.54	21,643.52	166.98	123,657,82	42,054.50

Source: Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin

The data for Human Development Index (HDI), Commercial Bank Lending (CBL), Finance House Lending (FCH), Development Bank Lending (NEXIM) and Market Capitalization (MKC) were presented in table one.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics results

	HDI	CBL	FCH	NEXIM	MKC
Mean	0.526583	12804.81	60.76500	36517897	21141.95
Median	0.530000	12940.41	47.74500	39160004	18040.41
Maximum	0.540000	21643.52	166.9800	85706366	42054.50
Minimum	0.500000	6685.850	23.77000	7637308.	9918.210
Std. Dev.	0.013621	4588.535	41.32003	22575160	10060.30
Skewness	-0.709077	0.282835	1.657968	0.675717	1.056905
Kurtosis	2.229961	2.307843	4.723458	2.974405	3.070244
Jarque-Bera	1.302060	0.399532	6.982872	0.913515	2.236564
Probability	0.521508	0.818922	0.030457	0.633334	0.326841
Sum	6.319000	153657.7	729.1800	4.38E+08	253703.4
Sum Sq. Dev.	0.002041	2.32E+08	18780.79	5.61E+15	1.11E+09
Observations	12	12	12	12	12

Source: Computer analysis using E-views 12.0

Summary of Descriptive Statistic

The descriptive characteristics of the variables are presented in Table 2. The mean Values of the HDI, CBL, FCH, DBL and MKC are 0.526583, 12804.81, 60.76500, 36517897 and 21141.95 while their median is 0.530000, 12940.41, 47.74500, 3916004 and 18040.41 respectively. The series depicts the maximum values of 0.540000, 21643.52, 166.9800, 85706366 and 42054.50 for HDI, CBL, FCH, DBL and MKC respectively. The minimum values are 0.500000 for HDI, 6685.850 for CBL, 23.77000 for FCH, 7637308 for DBL and 9918.210 for MKC. Commercial bank lending, finance house lending, development bank lending and market capitalization rate are positively skewed towards normality as evidenced by the positive sign of the skewness while human development index are negatively skewed.

Restatement and test of hypotheses

1. H_0 : There is no significant relationship between Commercial bank lending and Human Development Index of Nigeria.

H_1 : There is a significant relationship between Commercial bank lending and Human Development Index of Nigeria.

2. H_0 : Finance House Lending has no significant relationship with Nigeria Human Development Index.

H_1 : Finance House Lending has significant relationship with Nigeria Human Development Index.

3. H_0 : Development Bank Lending has no significant effect on Human Development Index of Nigeria.

H_1 : Development Bank Lending has no significant effect on Human Development Index of Nigeria.

4. H_0 : There is no significant relationship between Market Capitalization and Human Development Index of Nigeria.

H_1 : There is significant relationship between Market Capitalization and Human Development Index of Nigeria.

Table 3: OLS Regression of Nigeria Human Development Index and Commercial Bank Lending, Finance House Lending, Development Bank Lending and Market Capitalization

Dependent Variable: HDI				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.490178	0.006863	71.42852	0.0000
CBL	2.94E-06	1.00E-06	2.929334	0.0220
FCH	-1.17E-05	0.000187	-0.062277	0.9521
DBL	1.87E-10	1.28E-10	1.462263	0.1871
MKC	-3.48E-07	8.38E-07	-0.415250	0.6904
R-squared	0.869916	Mean dependent var		0.526583
Adjusted R-squared	0.795583	S.D. dependent var		0.013621
S.E. of regression	0.006158	Akaike info criterion		-7.047630
Sum squared resid	0.000265	Schwarz criterion		-6.845586
Log likelihood	47.28578	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-7.122434
F-statistic	11.70288	Durbin-Watson stat		1.869703
Prob(F-statistic)	0.003211			

Source: Computer analysis using E-views 12

Decision: The result showed that Commercial Bank Lending has positive and significant effect on HDI while Finance House Lending and Market Capitalization have negative and insignificant effect on HDI. Development Bank Lending (DBL) has positive and insignificant effect on human development index of Nigeria within the period of the study. The result of Durbin-Watson stat of 1.869703 and the probability of 0.003211 which is less than 0.05 level of significance. The OLS regression in table 3 implies that all the independent variables taken together significantly affect human development index in Nigeria. Thus, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative that Commercial Bank Lending (CBL), Finance House Lending (FCH), Development Bank Lending (DBL) and Market Capitalization (MKC) do influence Human Development Index.

Summary and Conclusion

The result of the analysis indicates that CBL has significant effect on human development index. This implies that commercial banks through their lending activities in Nigeria aided in economic development and poverty reduction by providing technical and financial assistance to investors and the government in implementing reforms or projects such as building schools, providing water and electricity, fighting disease, and protecting the environment. The result of finance house lending on Nigerian human development implies that finance houses have not provided enough financial and technical assistance to Nigerians to enable them to own their own homes or build houses for rentals which could have given them a greater access to basic goods and services, as well as investment in human capital and knowledge.

On the hand, the result of effect of development bank lending on human development index in Nigeria shows an insignificant positive relationship with the dependent variable, indicating that development bank lending through their capital formation and allocation role has not allocated enough capital to entrepreneurs and investors in a significant way of enhancing economic situation of the nation through human development

strategy. Then the result of relationship between market capitalization and human development index show market capitalization has negative and insignificant relationship with human development index. Indicating that investing in Nigerian capital market has not improved the standard of living of Nigeria. Again, investors have not made enough money from Nigerian capital market.

This study concludes that Nigerian human development index remains low due to unavailability of funds for investment and development as the result of the analysis indicates that only commercial banking lending has positive and significant effect on HDI in Nigeria. To curb these ugly situations, the monetary authority has to develop and implement investor friendly policy for development bank, finance houses, and capital market, because only the commercial banks cannot meet up with the fund requirement of these individuals.

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